

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR MOTIF

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Abstract: This article provides information on the concept of the motif, its distinct identity and basic functions, the correct analysis of motifs compared to themes, and criteria for identifying motifs in works of literature.

Key words: Motif, thematics, aesthetics, plot, theme, poetics, criticism, narrative, criteria.

Motif has been studied as a research object of lots of fields such as psychology, literature, music, art and biology. The word “motif” is noted as multi-meaning term in existing dictionaries and its lexical meaning is explained on the basis of the French words: “tune”, “melody” and Latin (or Greek) word “move”.

Working through the tangle of definitions for motif requires a lot of effort because the term appears in many academic disciplines and has a wide range of uses in literary criticism. This reality is further complicated by the multilingual research community, where different languages might contribute different nuances to the concept of motif. Aesthetics and thematology, often known as thematics, are the two main sciences that investigate themes.

Reductively speaking, there is a consensus among literary dictionaries about the definition of motif: it is a recurring element. They are in fact movable by nature. They can be investigated diachronically as a component of historical poetics. They can all be evaluated simultaneously for their individual contributions to a single work. Both strategies are helpful and advantageous to both parties. Before the word motif made its way from French into English, it underwent a few changes. As mentioned above, the term "motivus" originated from the Latin *motivus*, which means "movement or cause

of movement." It took on other meanings in French, such as "the subject that dominates a work" or "reason for acting." It was initially employed in music (1703), painting (1824), and later other arts. Therefore, the term motif frequently appears in a diachronic sense in the study of comparative literature (e.g., folkloristics), as a repeating feature in numerous works, such as the man who is fatally bewitched by a fairy lady, or the "loathly lady" who is actually beautiful. Similarly, migratory plots (also known as "sujets itinerants"), like "the abduction of the bride" and "the helpful beast," are described by Boris Tomashevsky as an object of historical poetics. This term bears similarities to an older one, *topos*, which in ancient literary theory denotes "recurrent concepts or formulas." For example, Lucretius frequently employed recurring themes in *De rerum natura* for pedagogical objectives, both as a compositional tool and as an artistic device influenced by Homer, Empedocles, and particularly Ennius' epic style.

It is important to mention that motifs are often confused with and overshadowed by themes. It is helpful to point out certain fundamental differences between motifs and other literary techniques, especially themes, because motifs and other terminology are frequently ambiguous. In reality, a number of dictionaries' articles on motif demonstrate this process of defining motifs in opposition to other concepts.

In academic literature as well as ordinary speech, themes and motifs are frequently used interchangeably. Actually, most people agree that motif and theme are the two most prevalent types of narrative recurrence. François Jost points out that even with unique nomenclature, there is still ambiguity: "What one critic designates as theme, another may call motif." However, it seems that everyone agrees that they are different and provide evidence against each other. I agree with literary academics who see the concepts as distinct yet complementary in this sense.

However, there is growing agreement that the key distinction between these categories—when referring to individual literary works—is that themes are abstract (e.g., concepts, main ideas, values) while motifs are typically concrete (such as recurring objects or expressions). A motif is, according to H. Porter Abbott, "a discrete thing, image, or phrase that is repeated in a narrative." In contrast, a theme is a more

abstract or broad idea that is implied by motifs, among other things. Greed is a topic, and a coin is a motif. There is non-Anglophone literature that makes this distinction. Bernard Dupriez, for instance, gives the following definition: "The work's theme will be more general and frequently more abstract than the motif. A single theme will have multiple motifs, while a single motif may serve multiple purposes. " Additional instances highlight their complimentary relationship, such as Edgar Allan Poe's *The Masque of the Red Death*, which uses the "clock" motif to represent the "time" topic. For example, *Wuthering Heights* employs the window motif to "support a highly complex interplay of three themes: escape, exclusion, and imprisonment." To put it succinctly, motifs contain implicit themes, but not the other way around.

Some of the duties of the motif have been fulfilled in the definition given in the paragraph before. Here, I want to clarify a few functional points without attempting to present a comprehensive list. We'll look at more performative qualities in later parts. Motifs can function as recurring, inanimate actors in the reading experience, contributing to the investigation of a work's issues and topics to varying degrees of intensity. "The motif, then, may become a part of the total perspective, pervading the book's atmosphere and becoming an important thread in the fabric of the work," is how Freedman puts this feature succinctly. This is the fundamental synecdochic role of themes. A motif has a specific role to play within the overall composition. However, how does a motif really work to enhance visual appeal and pleasure? Generally speaking, a theme supports the structural, emotive, and cognitive parts of a literary work, either partially or entirely.

From a structural standpoint, the motif could aid in explaining the story's action. Its consistent presence strengthens the narrative's coherence and makes the work easier for readers to follow and experience. Fitzgerald's "*The Great Gatsby*" incorporates the green light motif into the narrative framework. The green color of the light, which appears at various times (early and late), symbolizes optimism, particularly Gatsby's wish to win Daisy's love again.

Therefore, motifs are worth investigating because they have these aesthetic and interpretive aspects that might enhance stories. Now, the focus shifts to applied theory for more accurate motif identification.

A motif's identification is dependent on a number of variables. The motif must, in all objective cases, draw attention to itself in some way. Subjectively, whether or not this method is purposeful, it depends on the reader's ability to identify and appreciate it. While certain motifs are ancillary to the work, others are important. Certain patterns are so delicate that it may take multiple readings or viewings to fully appreciate them.

The presence of a motif in a literary work can be determined by two basic criteria: avoidability (or unlikelihood) and frequency. A motif must appear frequently, but the presence of a motif is not determined by a set number of instances. This depends on the work and its length. The motif needs to be employed more frequently than just in coincidental or necessary situations. Motifs need to "permeate the atmosphere sufficiently to assure that they will be at least subliminally felt," to put it simply.”

"The contexts in which the references appear or the uses to which they are put (extra literal uses, for example) do not demand references from the field of the motif," according to the second factor, avoidability, is defined. The events must somehow grab the reader's attention, both by their frequent occurrence and their varied applications. For instance, it's hard to ignore cars in a story about a mechanic, particularly if the garage serves as the primary scene. Nonetheless, allusions to cars and things that resemble cars in improbable situations may indicate the presence of an automobile motif.

I have demonstrated the unique identification of motifs and their diachronic and synchronic functions in order to support the usefulness of motifs in the literary narratives. It was required to define motifs initially because there are many interpretations and uses of the term, particularly when compared to themes. Their distinct identity and artistic significance have been highlighted by Freedman's thesis, which has been further developed by contemporary narrative theory. By presenting some basic functions of motifs, the comparison between motif and theme, and criteria

for identifying motifs in literary works, I have also made a little contribution to motif theory.

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